

**DEVELOPMENT OF METHODS OF CALCULATION AND FORECASTING OF THE SPECIFIC
ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION OF A MINING ENTERPRISE**

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ABSTRACT

Target. Improving the efficiency of relay protection and automation in technological power supply schemes of a high-mountain mine based on the results of experimental studies using statistical methods. This will increase the safety of electrical installations in networks of various voltages when expanding the front of mining, both underground and open-pit methods, as well as monitor electricity consumption and obtain an economic effect by improving the operation of relay protection.

Methodology. In this work, to determine the admittance, the method of artificial displacement of the neutral of the network relative to the ground from an external source of current was used, as well as the method of imposing a direct operating current on the working high-voltage network. The analysis of work in the field of increasing the operational reliability of power supply for developing areas of ore mining in a high-mountain mine, mine, open-pit and laboratory experimental research, mathematical and physical modeling, as well as theoretical analysis and generalization of research results using standard and new methods with the participation of the authors was also carried out.

Results. The parameters of electricity consumption were determined for individual technological and auxiliary sections of the quarry (overburden, mining of copper ore, loading from a dump of quartzite, loading from dumps of barite ore, mining of basalt stone, crushing of basalt stone). A method has also been developed for predicting the specific power consumption for individual technological sections of the open pit with the use of modern software. To improve the selectivity of relay protection, the currents of three- and two-phase short circuits in the networks with a voltage of 6 kV in the open pit are calculated, experimental studies on single-phase short circuits in the networks of the open pit and the concentrating plant are presented. Recommendations are given on the values of the settings of the relay protection against short circuits and on the use of directional protection against single-phase earth faults. In general, the proposed recommendations make it possible to carry out current control of electricity consumption and obtain an economic effect by improving the operation of relay protection.

Scientific novelty. Based on the data obtained for all divisions and for the three selected types of regression equations, the following relation is fulfilled: $F(\alpha, k_1, k_2) < F_{\text{вычисл.}}$. This indicates the adequacy of all the dependences obtained and gives reason to assert that all the obtained dependences are valid and can be used for calculations. As the simplest for engineering calculations, a linear dependence on i is recommended. A graph-analytical method for studying average electrical loads by month, quarter and year according to the corresponding average load schedules is also recommended.

Practical significance. Recommendations are given on the values of the settings of the relay protection against short circuits and on the use of directional protection against single-phase earth faults. Electricity consumption by subdivisions of the open pit of the Mining and Processing Plant has been determined, and a relatively good rhythm of the operation of electrical equipment has been shown. This makes it possible to use the obtained average data on electricity consumption in practice. In particular, when monitoring power consumption using electronic meters, it is recommended to compare the registered values of the specific monthly power consumption with the data obtained: overburden: $W_{sp.m} = 1.68 \text{ kWh} / t$; for the extraction of copper ore: $W_{sp} = 0.88 \text{ kWh} / t$; for loading from a dump of quartzite: $W_{sp} = 1.36 \text{ kWh} / t$ and barite ore: $W_{sp} = 1.36 \text{ kWh} / t$; for the extraction of basalt stone: $W_{sp} = 1.54 \text{ kWh} / t$. In general, the proposed recommendations make it possible to carry out current control of electricity consumption and obtain an economic effect by improving the operation of relay protection.

Prospective studies. It is noted that the introduction of automated geoinformation systems of the new generation, such as GIS K-MINE® (developer – "KAI Scientific and Industrial Enterprise" LLC (Ukraine), will allow to increase work productivity by 50% or more due to the use of optimization tasks, as well as speed up processes several times approval of mining technical documentation with controlling bodies by transferring it in electronic form.

Keywords: relay protection, automation, technological schemes, power supply, high-mountain mine, statistical methods, efficiency, work safety

Introduction

The problem of a constant increase in electricity consumption at mining enterprises is directly related to the tasks of improving the quality and saving electricity [1]. At many enterprises, the issues of rational use of electricity are still not given due attention; the values of specific energy consumption standards and ways of possible reduction through the use of new technologies are not analyzed [2]. Also, the issues of forecasting electricity consumption are not considered, which is important when planning specific consumption rates [3]. Electrical networks with a voltage of 6 kV of the mine in question developed gradually as the number of mining operations increased and, given their expected volume, cannot fully provide reliable power supply to the developing areas of underground and open-pit mining at the mine [4]. Therefore, an increase in power consumption, the need to ensure higher reliability and flexibility of the power supply system for mining operations and the safety of electrical installations in networks of various voltages when expanding the scope of mining operations, both underground and open-pit, is an important scientific and practical problem that requires an urgent solution [5].

The object of the study is the technology and technical means for power supply to developing ore mining sites at a mining enterprise. One of the most problematic areas is the difficulty in operating cable networks with a voltage of 6 kV, caused by breakdowns of cable insulation simultaneously in different sections of the cable network during a short circuit (short circuit) to ground in one of its sections [6].

The purpose of the study is to develop a methodology for calculating and forecasting the specific power consumption of a mining enterprise based on the results of experimental studies using statistical and graphic-analytical methods. This will improve the safety of electrical installations in networks of various voltages when expanding the scope of mining operations, as well as carry out ongoing monitoring of electricity consumption and obtain an economic effect by improving the operation of relay protection. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve such problems.

1. Perform a technological audit and measure short circuit currents to ground.

2. Develop a methodology for predicting specific power consumption for individual technological sections of the quarry using modern software.

3. Give recommendations on the settings of relay protection against short circuits and on the use of directional protection against single-phase ground faults.

Research methods

During the study, complex methods of direct ground fault were used to determine the admittance, a method using an artificial displacement of the network neutral relative to the ground from an external current source, as well as a method of imposing a constant operating current on a high-voltage operating network. An analysis of work in the field of increasing the operational reliability of power supply to developing ore mining sites at a mining enterprise, mine, quarry and laboratory experimental studies, mathematical and physical modeling, as well as theoretical analysis and generalization of research results using standard and new methods were also carried out [7].

Research results

Analysis of load diagrams of technological departments of a high-mountain mine. The research was carried out at the quarry of a mining and processing plant, which produces copper and barite ore, extracts quartzite and a number of additional works. The quarry is a large production unit, the power consumption of which is greatly influenced by a number of mining, geological and organizational factors. Thus, the monthly power consumption of the quarry varies within certain limits randomly. These changes have a certain impact on the values of specific power consumption and energy losses in the elements of the power supply system. In order to outline possible ways of rational energy consumption in a quarry, it is necessary to analyze the electricity consumption graphs for the main divisions of the quarry using methods of mathematical statistics [8].

Calculation diagram of quarry networks

To calculate short-circuit currents, a design diagram (Figure 1) and an equivalent circuit (Figure 2) of the quarry networks are drawn up..

Figure 1. Calculation diagram of the quarry network

Figure 2. Replacement diagram of the quarry network

The dispersion of discrete random variables from the mathematical expectation is characterized by the variance:

$$D[x] = M\{x - M[x]\}^2 \tag{2}$$

To estimate the dispersion of quantities in practical calculations, the standard deviation is more often used:

$$\sigma[x] = \sqrt{D[x]} \tag{3}$$

The accuracy of statistical estimates can be characterized by a confidence interval $(\theta^* - \delta, \theta^* + \delta)$, which covers the unknown parameter θ with a given reliability γ :

$$P[\theta^* - \delta < \theta < \theta^* + \delta] = \gamma \tag{4}$$

When determining the width of the confidence interval, as well as for a number of other statistical estimates, the Student distribution is used, characterized by the parameter:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - M[x]}{S} \cdot \sqrt{n} \tag{5}$$

where \bar{x} – sample mean; S – “corrected” standard deviation; n – sample size.

When analyzing statistical dependencies, it becomes necessary to describe these dependencies in the form of mathematical expressions that take into account the relationships between random variables. The construction of such dependencies is carried out using the theory of regression analysis. The main task of the

analysis is to study the relationship between the resulting feature y and the observed feature x , and to evaluate the regression function [9].

If the value of r is close to one, then there is a close relationship between the values of x and y , approaching a functional dependence; when r is close to zero, the relationship is random and cannot be represented in the form of an equation. The considered concepts of statistical assessment and analysis of random variables will be used in the future in the analysis of power consumption processes in a quarry [10, 11].

$$r = \frac{\frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot y_i - \frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i - \frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{\sqrt{\left[\frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \left(\frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^2 \right] \cdot \left[\frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 - \left(\frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \right)^2 \right]}} \quad (6)$$

where x_i, y_i – values of random variables under study at the i -th observation; n – number of observations.

Electricity consumption at the quarry is accounted for in the following technological for eight Departments, such as, (kWh):

1) overburden; 2) mining of copper ore; 3) loading from a quartzite dump; 4) loading barite ore from a dump; 5) extraction of basalt stone; 6) crushing of basalt stone; 7) administrative building; 8) mechanical workshop.

Energy consumption data for each department is recorded in the memory of electronic meters and is the initial information for analyzing load graphs. Due to some arrhythmia in the operation of technological equipment, fluctuations in power consumption may be observed throughout the day, weeks, months, quarters and years. Therefore, one of the tasks of analyzing load diagrams is to identify these fluctuations, assess their impact on the value of specific power consumption and ways to eliminate them.

There is also a need to determine the value of the mathematical expectation of power consumption for a certain period of time (month, quarter, year). It is also necessary to estimate the value of the confidence interval characterizing the spread of fluctuations in power consumption from the value of its mathematical expectation. The values of mathematical expectation and confidence interval are calculated using methods of statistical mathematics. To analyze electricity consumption for the period under study, the following are considered: by month - average monthly load graphs; by

Methodology for calculating electrical loads

When analyzing the operating modes of electrical receivers of industrial enterprises, the following types of loads are usually considered: active power, current and reactive power. When analyzing power consumption for individual technological divisions of the quarry, we use monthly power consumption as the studied parameter [12, 13].

The closeness of the connection between random variables x, y is characterized by the pair correlation coefficient (6).

quarter – averaged quarterly load graphs; by year – averaged annual load graphs [14, 15].

Graphic-analytical method for studying average monthly electrical loads

When analyzing fluctuations in electricity consumption within each month, it is necessary to find out whether there is any pattern of changes in electricity consumption or not. To carry out such an analysis, it is necessary to construct average monthly load graphs for each of the quarry divisions, representing the dependence of the average monthly power consumption W_{month} within five years:

$$W_{month} = f(i) \quad (7)$$

Average monthly power consumption W_{month} represents the arithmetic average of electricity consumption in the same month when considered for all years:

$$W_{month,i} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n W_{month,i,j}}{n}, \quad (8)$$

where i – number of the month in question; j – year number; n – number of years.

Based on the power consumption data obtained at the quarry using expression (8), the average monthly values of power consumption were calculated for the quarry divisions, which are given in Table 1. To assess the degree of fluctuation in power consumption and establish patterns of power consumption by month over five years, it is necessary to statistically process the data in Table 1

Table 1.

Average monthly power consumption by technological divisions of the quarry (W, kWh)							
Months							
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Overburden (No. 1)							
841517	783740	766650	762600	746520	787520	767980	800760
Copper ore mining (No. 2)							
74567	72600	80267	72833	75567	76433	76533	72833
Loading quartzites from the dump (No. 3)							
33383	35960	42360	43900	41540	37140	40800	39060
Loading barite ore from a dump (No. 4)							
27731	24187	24341	27363	24325	35462	26600	25792
Extraction of basalt stone (No. 5)							
3227	1080	3327	2033	2000	4000	2780	1300
Crushing basalt stone (No. 6)							
2980	3285	5170	6617	5167	4780	3532	6127
Administrative building (No. 7)							
7067	8060	7860	5860	5325	5000	2000	3400
Mechanical workshop (No. 8)							
23333	24120	23260	19120	16920	21920	9580	10000

for compliance with any distribution law and determine the following statistical indicators: mathematical expectation $M[W_{month}]$ power consumption values, standard deviation, confidence intervals. It is also necessary to perform a regression analysis to determine the pattern of power consumption for each of the technological divisions of the quarry [16, 17]. Systematic processing of the data shown in Table 1 was carried out using modern software. The analysis showed that, by the months of the years under study, the amount of electricity consumption in all divisions of the quarry follows the normal distribution law [18, 19].

Calculated mathematical expectation values $M[W_{month}]$, standard deviation S_n and the value of the confidence interval $t_{\alpha,k} \cdot S_n$ are given in Table 2. The value of the confidence interval was determined using the value of the Student coefficient $t_{\alpha,k}$ taken at the confidence level $p = 0,95$ (at significance level $\alpha = 0,05$) and number of measurements $n = 12$. For these values, the number of degrees of freedom is: $k = n - 2 = 10$ and $t_{0,05;10} = 2,23$. Using computer software, regression analysis was performed according to Table 1.

Table 2.

Statistical processing data (kWh)								
Department number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$M[W_{month}]$	802737	74958	38614	24061	2035	4429	5303	17919
S_n	58393	2198	3160	3071	1593	1569	1872	5155
$t_{\alpha,k} \cdot S_n$	130217	4902	7048	6848	3600	4361	4174	11496

In order to increase the reliability of the analysis for approximating power consumption dependencies W_{month} starting from month number the regression equations were proposed:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{month} &= a_0 + a_1 \cdot i \\ W_{month} &= a_2 \cdot \exp(a_3 \cdot i) \\ W_{month} &= a_4 + a_5 \cdot i + a_6 \cdot i^2 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6$ - coefficients determined using the least squares method (OLS). It is better to use different symbols, i.e. a_0 and a_1 for the first equation, a_2 and a_3 - for the second, a_4, a_5, a_6 - for the third.

The adequacy of regression equations (8-10) or (9) is determined using the Fisher criterion. Based on the results of the calculations performed for the quarry divisions, the following dependencies were obtained for eight Departments, such as, (kWh):

1) for stripping:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{month} &= 7,61 \cdot 10^5 + 6,49 \cdot 10^3 \cdot i \\ W_{month} &= 7,63 \cdot 10^5 \cdot e^{7,5 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot i} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$W_{month} = 8,47 \cdot 10^5 - 3,04 \cdot 10^4 \cdot i + 2,83 \cdot 10^3 \cdot i^2$$

2) for the extraction of copper ore:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{month} &= 7,56 \cdot 10^4 - 99,2 \cdot i \\ W_{month} &= 7,55 \cdot 10^4 \cdot e^{-2,54 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot i} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$W_{month} = 7,42 \cdot 10^4 + 5,08 \cdot 10^2 \cdot i - 46,7 \cdot i^2$$

3) for loading quartzites from a dump:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{month} &= 3,89 \cdot 10^4 - 47,3 \cdot i \\ W_{month} &= 3,86 \cdot 10^4 \cdot e^{-6,35 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot i} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$W_{month} = 3,44 \cdot 10^4 + 1,86 \cdot 10^3 \cdot i - 146 \cdot i^2$$

4) for loading barite ore from a dump:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{month} &= 2,78 \cdot 10^4 - 5,74 \cdot i \\ W_{month} &= 2,81 \cdot 10^4 \cdot e^{-2,54 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot i} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$W_{month} = 2,53 \cdot 10^4 + 449 \cdot i - 77,6 \cdot i^2$$

5) for the extraction of basalt stone:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{month} &= -3,22 \cdot 10^2 + 6,65 \cdot 10^2 \cdot i \\ W_{month} &= 1,84 \cdot 10^3 \cdot e^{3,33 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot i} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$W_{month} = 7,47 \cdot 10^3 - 2,93 \cdot 10^3 \cdot i + 299,6 \cdot i^2$$

6) for crushing basalt stone:

$$W_{month} = 2,73 \cdot 10^3 + 639,4 \cdot 10^2 \cdot i$$

$$W_{month} = 2,85 \cdot 10^3 \cdot e^{0,146 \cdot i} \quad (15)$$

$$W_{month} = 15,7 + 2,68 \cdot 10^3 \cdot i - 291,3 \cdot i^2$$

7) for administrative building:

$$W_{month} = 2,18 \cdot 10^3 - 288,3 \cdot i$$

$$W_{month} = 6,94 \cdot 10^3 \cdot e^{-5,23 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot i} \quad (16)$$

$$W_{month} = 1,02 \cdot 10^4 - 1,58 \cdot 10^3 \cdot i + 99,5 \cdot i^2$$

8) for mechanical workshop:

$$W_{month} = 2,26 \cdot 10^3 - 727 \cdot i$$

$$W_{month} = 2,22 \cdot 10^7 \cdot e^{-4,03 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot i} \quad (17)$$

$$W_{month} = 3,05 \cdot 10^4 - 4,09 \cdot 10^3 \cdot i + 258,7 \cdot i^2$$

The values of the correlation coefficient r , which characterizes the close relationship between power consumption and the number of month i , are given in Table 3.

Table 3.

Correlation coefficients for power consumption regression equations

Department number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
r	0,4007	-0,1627	-0,0479	-0,6742	0,4076	0,7625	-0,5553	-0,0851

The obtained regression equations were checked for adequacy using the Fisher criterion. The results of these checks are given in Table 4-6. Please write the criterion in the form used and describe $\alpha, K_1, K_2 S^2$.

As can be seen from the data obtained, presented in Tables 4-6, for all divisions and for the three selected types of regression equations, the following relation is satisfied: $F(\alpha, k_1, k_2) < F_{calc.}$, which indicates the adequacy of all obtained dependencies. This gives grounds

to assert that all the obtained dependencies are valid and can be used for calculations. A linear relationship is recommended as the simplest for engineering calculations W_{month} from i . From the data in Table 3 it follows that the most correlated are the power consumption dependencies W_{month} for the following divisions of the quarry: stripping, loading barite ore from the dump, mining of basalt stone, crushing of basalt stone, administrative building.

Table 4.

Significance of linear regression equation

Department number	$S^2, (kWh)^2$	W, kWh	W_1, kWh	W_{res}, kWh	$F(\alpha, k_1, k_2)$	$F_{calc.}$
1	$3,15 \cdot 10^9$	$3,75 \cdot 10^{10}$	$1,26 \cdot 10^{10}$	$2,49 \cdot 10^{10}$	4,96	5,03
2	$5,18 \cdot 10^6$	$2,99 \cdot 10^7$	$1,04 \cdot 10^7$	$1,95 \cdot 10^7$	4,96	5,4
3	$1,1 \cdot 10^7$	$1,07 \cdot 10^8$	$4,39 \cdot 10^7$	$6,31 \cdot 10^7$	4,96	6,93
4	$5,66 \cdot 10^6$	$6,03 \cdot 10^7$	$2,34 \cdot 10^7$	$3,69 \cdot 10^7$	4,96	6,2
5	$2,71 \cdot 10^7$	$2,02 \cdot 10^8$	$1,01 \cdot 10^8$	$1,01 \cdot 10^8$	4,96	5,45
6	$1,29 \cdot 10^6$	$2 \cdot 10^6$	$1,63 \cdot 10^6$	$3,7 \cdot 10^5$	4,96	5,84
7	$2,67 \cdot 10^6$	$2,9 \cdot 10^7$	$1,04 \cdot 10^7$	$1,86 \cdot 10^7$	4,96	5,86
8	$2,17 \cdot 10^7$	$1,02 \cdot 10^9$	$8,5 \cdot 10^8$	$1,7 \cdot 10^8$	4,96	5,65

where DN – Department number, $\alpha=0,05, k_1=1, k_2=10, m=5$.

Table 5.

Significance of exponential regression equation

Department number	α	k_1	k_2	m	$S_1^2, (kWh)^2$	W, kWh	W_1, kWh	W_{res}, kWh	$F(\alpha, k_1, k_2)$	$F_{calc.}$
1	0,05	1	10	5	$3,15 \cdot 10^3$	$3,75 \cdot 10^{10}$	$1,25 \cdot 10^{10}$	$2,5 \cdot 10^{10}$	4,96	5,05
2	0,05	1	10	5	$5,18 \cdot 10^6$	$2,99 \cdot 10^7$	$1,04 \cdot 10^7$	$1,95 \cdot 10^7$	4,96	5,3
3	0,05	1	10	5	$1,1 \cdot 10^7$	$1,07 \cdot 10^8$	$4,38 \cdot 10^7$	$6,32 \cdot 10^7$	4,96	6,9
4	0,05	1	10	5	$5,66 \cdot 10^6$	$6,03 \cdot 10^7$	$2,26 \cdot 10^7$	$3,77 \cdot 10^7$	4,96	6
5	0,05	1	10	5	$2,71 \cdot 10^7$	$2,02 \cdot 10^8$	$8,13 \cdot 10^7$	$1,21 \cdot 10^8$	4,96	5,41
6	0,05	1	10	5	$1,29 \cdot 10^6$	$2 \cdot 10^6$	$1,28 \cdot 10^6$	$7,2 \cdot 10^5$	4,96	6,3
7	0,05	1	10	5	$2,67 \cdot 10^6$	$2,9 \cdot 10^7$	$1,07 \cdot 10^7$	$1,83 \cdot 10^7$	4,96	5,82
8	0,05	1	10	5	$2,17 \cdot 10^7$	$1,02 \cdot 10^9$	$8,67 \cdot 10^8$	$1,53 \cdot 10^8$	4,96	5,61

That is, in these divisions, power consumption is subject to certain dependencies on the number of the month (season). For the departments of copper ore mining, loading quartzites from a dump, and a mechanical

workshop, the dependence of power consumption is largely determined by random factors, which corresponds to the nature of the work of these departments [20, 21].

Table 6.

Significance of parabolic regression equation

Department number	α	k_1	k_2	m	$S^2, (\text{kWh})^2$	W, kWh	W_1, kWh	$W_{\text{res}}, \text{kWh}\cdot\text{h}$	$F(\alpha, k_1, k_2)$	$F_{\text{calc.}}$
1	0,05	1	10	5	$1,89\cdot 10^9$	$3,75\cdot 10^{10}$	$7,55\cdot 10^9$	$2,99\cdot 10^{10}$	4,96	5,12
2	0,05	1	10	5	$4,44\cdot 10^6$	$2,99\cdot 10^7$	$8,88\cdot 10^6$	$2,1\cdot 10^7$	4,96	5,4
3	0,05	1	10	5	$7,33\cdot 10^6$	$1,07\cdot 10^8$	$2,93\cdot 10^7$	$7,77\cdot 10^7$	4,96	6,95
4	0,05	1	10	5	$4,54\cdot 10^6$	$6,03\cdot 10^7$	$1,81\cdot 10^7$	$4,22\cdot 10^7$	4,96	6,27
5	0,05	1	10	5	$1,67\cdot 10^7$	$2,02\cdot 10^8$	$1,24\cdot 10^8$	$7,8\cdot 10^7$	4,96	5,52
6	0,05	1	10	5	$3,96\cdot 10^5$	$2\cdot 10^6$	$3,96\cdot 10^5$	$1,6\cdot 10^6$	4,96	6,83
7	0,05	1	10	5	$1,22\cdot 10^6$	$2,9\cdot 10^7$	$4,88\cdot 10^6$	$2,41\cdot 10^7$	4,96	5,9
8	0,05	1	10	5	$1,16\cdot 10^7$	$1,02\cdot 10^9$	$4,63\cdot 10^8$	$5,57\cdot 10^9$	4,96	5,71

According to the table. 1, for graphical analysis, average monthly power consumption graphs were constructed for eight technological divisions of the quarry (Departments). As an example, these dependencies for the quarry divisions (overburden, department No. 1) are presented in Fig. 3. The dotted line in the indicated figure shows the values of the mathematical expectation. Analysis of the graph (see Fig. 3) shows that there is no

trend towards an increase or decrease in power consumption during the month [22, 23]. To analyze power consumption within a quarter, it is necessary to consider the average quarterly graphs of electrical loads for all divisions of the quarry. In the same way, as in the analysis of average monthly load graphs, the values of power consumption are determined W . These data are shown in Table. 7.

Figure 3. Average monthly power consumption chart for overburden

Study of average quarterly graphs of electrical loads

Statistical processing of data in Table 7 showed that within the quarter the amount of electricity consumption W in all divisions of the quarry it obeys the

normal distribution law by departments and quarters of the year [24, 25].

Table 7.

Average quarterly power consumption by technological divisions of the quarry (κWh)

I	II	III	IV
Overburden (No. 1)			
2406820	2296640	2410720	2174600
Copper ore mining (No. 2)			
227483	224833	223400	224300
Loading quartzites from the dump (No. 3)			
114280	122580	116720	123275
Loading barite ore from a dump (No. 4)			
72287	77166	77111	52137
Extraction of basalt stone (No. 5)			
7634	8033	3200	1800
Crushing basalt stone (No. 6)			
11435	18401	15378	16121
Administrative building (No. 7)			
22400	15120	7800	16000
Mechanical workshop (No. 8)			
71180	57960	32980	54375

Calculated mathematical expectation values $M[W]$, standard deviation S_n and the value of the confidence interval $t_{\alpha,k} \cdot S_n$, defined in the same way as above are given in Table 8.

Table 8.

Statistical processing data								
Department number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$M[\overline{W}_{kW}], \text{ kW}\cdot\text{h}$	2322195	224991	119214	69675	5167	14700	15330	54124
$S_n, \text{ kW}\cdot\text{h}$	111705	1732	4415	11914	1174	1039	3279	11591
$t_{\alpha,k} S_n, \text{ kW}\cdot\text{h}$	480331	7447	1897	51229	5050	13200	14100	51131

To approximate the dependences of power consumption \overline{W}_{kW} as a function of the quarter number, expressions of the same type were used as in the study of average monthly electricity consumption [26, 27].

Forecasting specific power consumption

When planning power consumption for subsequent years and for declaring the value of the thirty-minute maximum power P_{30} it is necessary to have an estimate of these quantities. Determining the forecast value of specific electricity consumption for one year in advance is based on a statistical analysis of changes in this value over a number of previous years. As follows from the analysis of existing methods for predicting electrical quantities, one of the most accurate methods for engineering solutions is forecasting using the concepts of autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation functions. For this case, a program has been developed to predict specific electricity consumption one year in advance. The use of the developed program for planning electricity consumption at mining and processing enterprises will make it possible to correctly distribute electricity resources among quarters of the next year, control actual electricity consumption and purposefully work to reduce it, due to which an appropriate economic effect can be obtained [28].

Thus, based on experimental studies using statistical methods, the authors determined the parameters of electricity consumption for individual technological and auxiliary sections of the quarry (overburden, copper ore mining, loading from quartzite dumps, loading from barite ore dumps, mining of basalt stone, crushing of basalt stone). A methodology for predicting specific power consumption for individual technological sections of the quarry using modern software has also been developed. To improve the selectivity of relay protection, the currents of three- and two-phase short circuits in the 6 kV networks of the quarry are calculated, and experimental studies of single-phase short circuits in the networks of the quarry and processing plant are presented. Based on the research carried out, recommendations were given on the settings of relay protection against short circuits and on the use of directional protection against single-phase ground faults. In general, the proposed recommendations allow for ongoing monitoring of electricity consumption and obtaining an economic effect by improving the operation of relay protection [29].

Promising areas of research

Further analysis of microprocessor relay protection in various industries using the results obtained in

the work is important and relevant. The developed methods for calculating and forecasting specific power consumption of mining enterprises can be further expanded through the use of rank analysis methods of neural networks. The use and adaptation of mathematical modeling of technological processes and automated geographic information systems of the new generation such as GIS K-MINE® (Krivoy Rog, Ukraine) and VENTSIM is relevant [30]. Unfinished sentence. And finally, as a result of the research, an assessment was made of the operational reliability of power supply to developing ore mining sites at a mining enterprise to ensure higher flexibility of the power supply system for mining operations. At the same time, the reliability and safety of electrical installations in networks of various voltages increases when the scope of mining operations is expanded by both underground and open-pit methods. The presented research results are important in the implementation of educational programs for training mining engineers, especially for distance learning during a pandemic. Based on the results of power consumption by divisions of a mining enterprise's quarry, a good rhythm of operation of electrical equipment is shown. This makes it possible to use the obtained average data on power consumption in practice [31, 32].

Conclusion

The obtained values of average power consumption and average specific power consumption (mathematical expectations) allow for ongoing monitoring of power consumption by quarry divisions. These indicators can be used to monitor the progress of the technological process and when modernizing the distribution networks of the quarry.

When monitoring electricity consumption using electronic meters, it is recommended to compare the recorded values of specific monthly electricity consumption with the obtained data, such as (kW*h/t):

overburden: $W_{ud, \text{month}}=1.68$; for copper ore mining: $W_{ud, \text{month}}=0.88$; for loading from a quartzite dump: $W_{ud, \text{month}}=1.36$; for the extraction of basalt stone: $W_{ud, \text{month}}=1.54$.

Comparing the actual values of specific power consumption with the recommended ones will make it possible to prevent excess energy consumption in individual technological processes. Due to the operational control of the operating modes of the quarry's electrical equipment, it is possible to reduce unproductive energy consumption and thereby obtain a corresponding economic effect.

Prospective Research. It was noted that the introduction of automated new generation geographic information systems such as GIS K-MINE® (developed by Scientific-Industrial Enterprise KAI, Ukraine) and VENTSIM are recommended will increase work productivity by 50% or more through the use of optimization tasks, as well as speed up several times the processes of coordinating mining technical documentation with regulatory authorities by transmitting it electronically.

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